

Classical Considerations Incorporated Into the Schrodinger Equation?

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The time-independent Schrodinger equation makes use of the classical potential $V(x)$ (in many cases) as well as a form which appears as conservation of energy, i.e. $KE(ave) + V(x) = E_n$. The question we ask is: Why is $\frac{\sum_p a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx)}{\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)}$ the average kinetic energy? If one accepts $\exp(ipx)$ as a kind of probability, then one may mathematically construct a mathematical average, but why is this particular average the one which should be used together with a classical $V(x)$? We argue that the answer may lie in the high energy limit of this term.

In particular, $\exp(ipx)$ describes a particle with momentum p (one dimension) and nonrelativistic kinetic energy $p^2/2m$. Thus, even though there is a wavelength \hbar/p , p and $p^2/2m$ apply to each x point. In a bound state, one would perform a time average and so $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are present, but these two should not distinguish between kinetic energy. Thus, for $a(p) = a(-p)$, $\frac{p^2/2m a(p) (\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx))}{a(p) (\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx))} = \frac{p^2/2m}{2 \cos(px)}$ which clearly shows the wavelength form. The kinetic energy, however, is still $p^2/2m$ at any x , so one should divide by $\cos(px)$. The question then becomes: What does one do if one has many $\pm p$ pairs as in the case of a $V(x)$? What average kinetic energy should be used? In such a case, one has: $\frac{\sum_p a(p) \cos(px)}{\sum_p a(p)}$ for probabilities for $a(p) = a(-p)$. In the case of any $a(p) = 1$ and the rest becoming 0, one should obtain $\cos(px)$ as the probability. Such a probability is associated with $p^2/2m$. Thus, $\frac{p^2/2m}{\cos(px)} = \frac{p^2/2m \cos(px)}{\cos^2(px)}$.

The point we wish to make is that even though $\exp(ipx)$ is linked with translational invariance, i.e. all x values, classically there is one p value at each x and this is linked to $V(x)$, the same $V(x)$ used in quantum mechanics. Thus, we suggest that the average form used for kinetic energy should comply approximately with $a(p(x)) = 1$ at x with $p(x)$ with the rest of the $a(p)$ values being 0 in order to obtain the high energy level classical result. This we suggest is why the average is consistent with classical mechanics. In the high energy limit, wavelengths become tiny and fit inside classical dx values, but one must still have one p map to each x (or $\pm p$ pair because of the time average). The quantum average form must be consistent with the result because the classical $V(x)$ is used. We suggest that this is why one uses the average. In other words, the very form of the Schrodinger equation is a priori consistent with classical conservation of energy which allows one to use $V(x)$ and to collapse the average kinetic energy form to a classical result for a particular $a(p) = 1$ with the rest of the $a(p)$ values being 0.

In other words, we suggest that one may take a smooth $V(x)$ and approximate it as $V(x) = \text{constant}(x)$ in each dx at x . The Schrodinger equation should be solved in each dx and this leads to free particle solutions in each dx which matches classical physics. This solution should be incorporated into whatever math form is used for $KE_{ave}(x)$.

The $\exp(ipx)$ Form

The quantum free particle wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$, does not exist in classical Newtonian mechanics, but the notion of a momentum p and kinetic energy $p^2/2m$ (non-relativistic) or $E = \sqrt{p^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4}$ relativistically does. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is not mutually exclusive from classical

physics, but it does introduce a wavelength, \hbar/p , which does not appear in classical physics, and which has important consequences. In previous notes, we have suggested that $\exp(ipx)$ is a mathematical probability which ensures conservation of momentum, but requires a second variable, x , and orthogonality in x to do so.

Given the classical understanding of p and $p^2/2m$ in $\exp(ipx)$ it seems that the classical concept $V(x)$ should also make sense. In other words, if $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability which conserves momentum, then many classical ideas still exist. If $V(x)$ still makes sense as an average potential energy at x , because \hbar/p implies that one does not know at which x a particle is, then the question becomes: How does one create $KE_{ave}(x)$?

If $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability, one may immediately write:

$$KE_{ave} = \left\{ \sum_p a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} \quad ((1))$$

The form ((1)), however, is strictly mathematical and we ask: How can one be sure that this really represents KE_{ave} ? Certainly one may write the classical conservation equation (from Newton's second law) using KE_{ave} , i.e. the time-independent Schrodinger equation:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((2)) \quad \text{using } ((1))$$

((2)), however, is again a math equation. It would need to be verified experimentally which has been done. We argue, however, that a justification of ((1)) should follow from classical physics because $V(x)$ and the concepts of p and $p^2/2m$ (nonrelativistic) come from classical physics.

If one solves ((2)) for $W = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ as a differential equation, then $W(x)$ has crests and troughs of different heights and widths, The heights are linked to the amount of time a particle spends in the base x region. The width represents x resolution. One may solve for E_n being very high in which case, one would expect to obtain classical physics, albeit a time average, i.e. one which combines $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$.

We suggest, however, that one may try to link ((1)) to classical physics in a different manner which justifies the mathematical form ((1)).

Step Function Potential

Even though ((1)) may be solved for W if $V(x)$ is a continuous function, such as $.5kx^2$ for an oscillator, there are cases of discontinuity in $V(x)$, such as the square well potential. In such a case, one solves ((1)) in each region (in $V(x)=-V_0$ and $V(x)=0$) and then tries to match $W(x)$ and dW/dx . In principle, all derivatives should match at the junction, but they do not. The same strategy applies for one dimensional reflection-refraction.

If one may use such potential discontinuity, then we suggest that it may be applied to approximate a smooth $V(x)$ because Newtonian mechanics suggests that $v(x)=\text{velocity}$ is constant in each dx . In Newtonian mechanics $dx \rightarrow 0$, but we suggest that physically this is not the case, there is always some finite width. If that is the case, then one has a constant potential in each dx and one essentially has a free particle solution in dx with a momentum matching

$p=mv(x)$ (nonrelativistic). One does not necessarily have to worry about matching $W(x)$ or derivatives. The question then becomes: How does one analyze $KE_{ave}(x)$ in such a case?

Given the form ((1)), one may notice that if $a(p)=a(-p)$, then $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)^2 \ p^2/2m \cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ is used if $a(p)=-a(-p)$.

$\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ indicate time averaging, i.e. combinations of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. It was already noted, however, that $\exp(ipx)$ is linked with a classical kinetic energy of $p^2/2m$ at each x point. Thus, if each dx corresponds to a particular $p(x)$, then one may imagine this associated with $\exp(ipx)$ if \hbar/p (or many wavelengths) fit within $\exp(ipx)$. As a result, it is also linked to $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ and:

$$p^2/2m = p^2/2m \cos(px)/\cos(px) = p^2/2m \sin(px)/\sin(px). \quad ((3))$$

As a result, in the high energy, classical limit, we suggest that whatever math form is used for $KE_{ave}(x)$ should allow for the possibility of the form ((3)). We suggest that the form ((1)) allows for ((3)) if one sets $a(p)=1$ for $p(x)$ at dx and the rest of the $a(p)$ s to 0. This is not the solution that one would obtain from the differential equation ((2)), but it is in keeping with a math solution for the case in which $V(x)$ is approximated by constant V_0 values in each dx .

Thus, we suggest that ((1)) is a reasonable form for $KE_{ave}(x)$ and that the justification comes from classical physics and the approximation of $V(x)$ with step functions such that one has free particle solutions (actually $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-ipx)$ combinations due to time averaging) in each dx .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the quantum free particle probability $\exp(ipx)$ allows one to mathematically write: $KE_{ave}(x) = \{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)p^2/2m \exp(ipx)\} / \{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)\}$. ((4)) Using conservation of average energy $KE_{ave}(x)+V(x)=E_n$, one may obtain a differential equation and solve for $W=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. One may check experimentally if one obtains the correct E_n values (or $E_{n+1}-E_n$).

We suggest that the math form uses for $KE_{ave}(x)$ should describe classical mechanics. We thus propose to take a smooth $V(x)$ and approximate it by $V(x)=\text{constant}(x)$ in each dx . In such a case, the time-dependent Schrodinger equation is a combination of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ in each dx with p constant i.e. a $p(x)$. This approach matches classical physics. We argue that ((4)) should mathematically allow for such a solution and it does, if one considers $a(p)=1$ for $p=p(x)$ in dx at x and the rest of the $a(p)$ s=0. Thus, we suggest that there is a classical reason for using $KE_{ave}()$ given by ((4)).